

X-ray blasts from awakening massive black holes

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Typical X-ray active galactic nuclei are known to vary on both short (hours) and long (years) timescales. However, the so-called X-ray quasi-periodic eruptions (QPEs), discovered in late 2018 [1], are surely an exotic and novel entry in the catalog of X-ray emitting sources. QPEs are X-ray bursts repeating every few hours in a quasi-periodic fashion, with a flux increase of more than one order of magnitude over a quiescence level (see Figure 1). QPEs have been found so far only in a handful of sources [1, 2, 3, 4].

Figure 1: X-ray light curve of the QPE source eRO-QPE2, adapted from [3].

QPEs' observational properties

QPEs have so far been associated with nearby ($z \sim 0.02 - 0.05$) galaxies with stellar masses of $M_{star} \approx 1 - 3 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$ [3]. Their optical spectra lack broad emission lines and no infrared photometry excess, associated with the dusty environment typical of active galactic nuclei, is observed [1, 2, 3]. However, narrow lines in the optical spectra suggest the presence of an ionizing source, weak in some QPE hosts, in addition to star formation [5]. These galaxies host massive black holes of $M_{BH} \approx 10^{5-7} M_{\odot}$ [5], a range which is intriguingly close to the elusive black hole population with intermediate mass [6]. Therefore, QPEs might provide a new channel to activate the nuclei of low-mass galaxies through transient accretion events, which is still a poorly studied regime in the black hole-galaxy co-evolution history [7].

The average recurrence time between consecutive eruptions in the X-ray light curve spans, from source to source (see Figure 1 for one example), within $\sim 2.5 - 18.5$ h, while the average duration of the eruptions is observed to be $\sim 0.5 - 7.0$ h [3]. The emission in quiescence (i.e. excluding the eruptions) is very soft (most observed X-ray signal below ~ 1 keV) and as bright as $0.3 - 1.6 \times 10^{41} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ between $0.5 - 2.0$ keV. At their peak the emission spectrum is harder, but still overall soft

(most observed X-ray signal below $\sim 2 - 2.5$ keV) and QPEs are as bright as $L_{0.5-2.0 \text{ keV}} \approx 10^{42} - 10^{43} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. Given the QPEs' black hole mass estimates [5], this suggests that they are close to being Eddington-limited.

Finding QPEs with eROSITA

QPEs have so far been discovered only through X-rays. Some of them have been found either serendipitously [1] or through dedicated searches in X-ray observations archives [2, 4]. The eROSITA X-ray telescope [8] currently provides the only blind and systematic way to find more QPEs as they happen [3]. eROSITA started the first of eight all-sky surveys (eRASS1-8) on 13 December 2019. In each survey, completed in six months, every point of the sky is observed for ~ 40 s every ~ 4 h with the number of times (typically a few) varying with the location in the sky, increasing towards high ecliptic latitudes [8]. A QPE candidate is found if an extragalactic source shows recurrent high-amplitude variability (see Figure 2 for an example), although follow-up with other X-ray instruments is needed given eROSITA's observational cadence and sampling (e.g. Figure 1 for the same source shown in Figure 2). In the first year of eROSITA operations two QPEs were found with this method [3] and similar rates are expected for the future.

Figure 2: eROSITA X-ray light curve (with red and orange highlighting faint and bright observations, respectively) of the QPE source eRO-QPE2, of which a continuous follow-up observation is shown in Figure 1. Reported from [3].

The origin of QPEs

The origin of QPEs is still open and debated. However, QPEs' X-ray properties are inconsistent with current models of radiation-pressure instabilities in an isolated accretion disk [3], although dedicated simulations will need to be performed in the future. Similarly, QPEs' multi-wavelength observational properties rule out a binary of massive black holes with mass-ratio close to unity [3]. Recently, models based on a massive black hole and

at least one stellar-mass companion have gained significant attention [9, 10, 11, 12, 13], a scenario often referred to as extreme mass-ratio in spiral (EMRI). EMRI scenarios for QPEs are qualitatively consistent with their multi-wavelength properties. First, QPEs' hosts are low-mass galaxies with massive black holes [3, 5], where nuclear star clusters are expected to be nearly ubiquitous [14], which is confirmed for at least two QPE sources [1, 15]. Second, QPEs have a high-incidence in young post-starburst galaxies [5]. Both these ingredients make a galactic nucleus prone to EMRI-like events [14]. These models are also able to reproduce the average periodicity and luminosity of QPEs. However, quantitative comparisons including a physical model for the X-ray emission still need to be performed.

Interestingly, EMRIs also emit gravitational wave signals detectable by future-generation instruments like LISA and Tianqin [13], although it is still unclear whether the same EMRI can be observed by both electromagnetic and gravitational waves detectors [16]. If confirmed, this would surely revolutionize the future of multi-messenger astronomy.

QPEs are more complicated than it seems

Models have so far been compared to QPEs observations only qualitatively, also because QPEs were initially considered as somewhat orderly pulses with a small scatter in the arrival times. However, performing follow-up on known QPE sources after months or even years helped to mount evidence of more complicated behavior. For instance, QPEs can disappear within a few years [4], which puts strong constraints on their duration, incredibly short compared to the lifetime of a galactic nucleus. Furthermore, a more thorough analysis on the X-ray properties of QPE sources is revealing that their time evolution is far more complex than a simple "quasi-periodicity" [17]. In [17] a tentative separation in two sub-classes of QPEs has been suggested. As a matter of fact, in two sources (namely GSN 069 and eRO-QPE2, [1, 3]), long and short recurrence times, as well as relatively stronger and weaker bursts, alternate [11, 17]. In other two sources (namely RX J1301.9+2747 and eRO-QPE1, [2, 3]) the timing properties can be complex and irregular: the scatter on arrival times is so high that the question as to whether there is a periodicity at all rises ([18]); and at times QPEs do not appear as isolated pulses, but rather as a chaotic mixture of bursts with different amplitudes overlapping in time [17]. An example of this is shown in Figure 3 for the source eRO-QPE1 [17].

Figure 3: X-ray light curve of the QPE source eRO-QPE1, adapted from [17]. The source underwent a very complex cycle with a chaotic mixture of bursts with different amplitude and overlapping in time (each shown in blue, while the total fit in green).

It is still early days, as this research field effectively started in 2019, but QPEs are surely the new frontier to study variable accretion onto massive black holes. Observations are revealing more and more details and models are being put forward at a fast pace. For the near future, new QPEs can be found with eROSITA and science teams of planned or proposed X-ray missions are investigating whether their instruments can be used to find and/or study QPEs. In the meantime, these questions remain unanswered: what are QPEs and how do they awake massive black holes in galactic nuclei?

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